

CHANGES IN DENTAL HARD TISSUES UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF ENERGY DRINKS IN MILITARY PERSONNEL AND IMPROVEMENT OF PREVENTIVE MEASURES

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Abstract. Energy drinks are used to increase physical endurance and alertness, improve reaction time, improve concentration, and stimulate metabolism during sports, driving, and other outdoor activities. The most commonly consumed energy drinks contain large amounts of "carbohydrates" such as glucose, fructose, sucrose, and synthetic maltodextrins. On the other hand, energy drinks contain "caffeine, plant extracts of guarana, ginseng, and ginkgo biloba, B vitamins, amino acids such as taurine, amino acid derivatives such as carnitine, and sugar derivatives."

Keywords. Caffeine, psychostimulant, taurine, etiopathogenetic views, platelet aggregation, tachycardia.

The composition of energy drinks is dangerous for dental health. Acids present in drinks create an environment that promotes the destruction of tooth enamel. It is important to understand that even with rare consumption of drinks, the negative impact on teeth can be significant[1,4].

According to various studies, the high acidity levels in energy drinks can cause a rapid decrease in the pH level in the mouth. When the pH level drops below 5.5, the process of demineralization of tooth enamel begins, making it vulnerable to caries. The sugar content is also a major problem, as it promotes plaque formation and the proliferation of bacteria that feed on sugar and secrete acid.

Experts recommend limiting the consumption of energy drinks or taking measures to reduce their negative impact. But not everyone is aware of how to properly care for their teeth after drinking such drinks. Acids in energy drinks (citric, phosphoric, etc.) lead to the gradual destruction of the protective layer of teeth. With regular consumption of drinks, the enamel becomes thinner, the teeth become more sensitive to temperature changes and irritants. If you brush your teeth immediately after drinking the drink, this can increase the damage to the enamel, since at the moment of weakening of the enamel, the effect of the toothbrush becomes even more aggressive [2,5].

Sugar in energy drinks also plays an important role. It is "food" for bacteria, which, when processing sugar, release acids. These acids further destroy enamel, which contributes to the development of caries. In addition, according to dental studies, energy drinks significantly increase the risk of caries, especially in people with reduced salivation or other oral features [2,5]. To reduce the risks, dentists recommend rinsing your mouth with water or using special products to neutralize acidity after drinking energy drinks.

When tooth enamel is damaged, the mouth becomes more susceptible to bacteria due to the lack of protection provided by the enamel. If bacteria gets into the teeth, it can lead to serious dental problems. Without enamel protection, teeth can become sensitive. This can cause pain and discomfort when eating certain foods. Inflammation of the roots of the teeth and bleeding gums can occur. Since caffeine destroys tooth enamel, teeth can be subject to

decay and decay. The consequences of decay can be very serious, since the enamel does not recover after damage. The type of acid and the ingredients included in the composition also affect the erosive potential of energy drinks.

Citric acid, also known as acidifier 330 in the International Food Additive Numbering System [3], is widely used in soft drinks. Due to its chelating ability, which is responsible for the removal of calcium from saliva and teeth, this acid is one of the most powerful. The citrate anion has the ability to chelate calcium. The chelating effect is supplemented by the erosive potential of the released proton ions. According to numerous studies, drinks containing citric acid with a low pH have the greatest erosive capacity[3,6].

It has been found that drinks containing citric acid have a higher erosive potential than drinks containing maleic acid. Surface degradation can also be adversely affected by the acidic nature of energy drinks. Subsurface ions such as Ca, Al and silicon will be lost. Surface degradation may begin. This may result in decreased wear resistance and surface roughness. Surface roughness due to wear and chemical degradation may also affect the "gloss" and consequently increase external staining. One study reported that resin materials are susceptible to surface roughness degradation after immersion in sports drinks. The pH of energy drinks may cause erosion of composite resins under acidic conditions. Acids contained in these drinks may penetrate the resin matrix and release unreacted monomers into the environment. This may result in decreased surface hardness values of composite resins[2,5].

Problems caused by energy drinks often begin with increased tooth sensitivity. When enamel is damaged, it stops performing its protective function, which leads to discomfort when eating hot, cold, sour and sweet foods. Gradually, the situation can worsen, and patients begin to suffer from chronic pain associated with enamel erosion.

Caries is the next serious consequence. On average, people who regularly consume energy drinks face the problem of caries much more often than those who avoid them. High acidity and sugar in the drinks create an ideal environment for the rapid reproduction of pathogenic bacteria, which leads to the rapid spread of caries.

Enamel erosion is another negative consequence that is difficult to correct without the intervention of a dentist. Deep erosion often requires the installation of crowns or veneers, which is associated with additional costs for dental treatment.

It is not easy to completely avoid harm when consuming energy drinks, but you can minimize the negative effects by following simple recommendations. First, it is important to limit the frequency of consumption. Dentists recommend consuming energy drinks only when necessary and avoiding their regular use.

Secondly, after taking energy drinks, it is useful to rinse your mouth with plain water or use a rinse with a neutralizing effect. This will help reduce the acidity in your mouth and protect your enamel from further destruction. Brushing your teeth immediately after drinking is not recommended - it is better to wait at least 30 minutes so that your saliva has time to neutralize some of the acids.

Thirdly, if you frequently consume energy drinks, it is advisable to use toothpastes and rinses containing fluoride. Fluoride helps strengthen enamel and reduce its susceptibility to destruction by acids. Those who often feel the need for energy and energy support should consider alternative ways to increase energy. For example, strong tea or natural coffee contain caffeine, but do not have the same level of acidity and sugar, which makes them less

harmful to teeth. Green tea, rich in antioxidants, also helps improve attention and concentration, but does not have a negative effect on enamel.

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Saliva is essential for maintaining oral health because it washes away food particles, neutralizes acids, and helps remineralize tooth enamel. The risk of dental problems such as cavities and bad breath increases when saliva production decreases. Energy drinks often contain artificial colors and additives that can cause tooth discoloration in the long term. Unsightly tooth discoloration can result from a combination of acidic properties and chromogens in the drinks. Long-term consumption of energy drinks can cause noticeable staining of teeth and can ruin the aesthetics of your smile.

Energy drink components may be particularly damaging to the teeth of children and adolescents because mineralization in immature permanent enamel is not complete, allowing for increased susceptibility to the aggressive nature (of these drinks). However, previous studies have shown inconclusive results when comparing the dissolution rates of primary and permanent enamel. In the present study, the percentage of mass loss in primary enamel samples was lower (although not statistically proven) compared to permanent enamel samples [6]. Primary enamel of teeth has a higher degree of porosity and a lower degree of mineralization than permanent enamel, suggesting that primary enamel is more susceptible to the effects of soft drinks.

In which the sensitivity of primary and permanent enamel to citric acid was studied, it was found that primary enamel was more susceptible to dissolution than its permanent counterpart. In this study, the primary enamel samples included small areas of dentin tissue, which may have affected the percentage of mass loss. A possible reason for the reduced mass loss of primary enamel could be the buffering properties of the organic components of dentin, and the collagen content served as a barrier to diffusion in the low pH environment of soft drinks. Dentists have a responsibility to advise their patients on the consumption of foods and drinks that may be detrimental to dental health. Most foods and drinks do not have a significant effect on dental health.

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Thus, regular consumption of energy drinks can cause irreparable harm to teeth, especially if preventive measures are not taken. Patients who care about their dental health should consider reducing the amount of energy drinks in their diet or replacing them with

drinks that are safer for teeth. It is also important to remember the need for regular oral care and timely visits to the dentist for professional consultation and prevention.

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